

[Instructions for Artifact Evaluation](#)
[Reviews for Artifact Evaluation](#)

Highly-Optimizing and Multi-Target Compiler for Embedded System Models

C++ Compiler Toolchain for the Component and Connector Language EmbeddedMontiArc

[Evgeny Kusmenko](#) [Bernhard Rumpe](#), Sascha Schneiders and [Michael von Wenckstern](#)

[For MontiSim please click here](#)

Contents for Supplementary Material according to Paper Outline:

[2 RUNNING EXAMPLE](#)

[3 PRELIMINARIES](#)

[4 TOOLCHAIN](#)

[6 CASE STUDY](#)

2 RUNNING EXAMPLE

Execute the Spectral Clusterer Running Example in your web-browser.

The WebAssembly module was created by the EmbeddedMontiArc compiler presented in the paper.

Please click at the picture below to run the example in a new tab. Please make sure that your browser supports WebAssembly. (For further information see [here](#)).

3 PRELIMINARIES

EmbeddedMontiArc models presented in **C&C Modeling and EmbeddedMontiArc**.

- ObjectDetector model with SpectralClusterer subcomponents
 - graphical C&C Model; layout is automatically generated (Please pay attention to the three different abstraction levels when browsing the models in a new tab)
[Open Graphical Model](#)
 - [Published Textual EmbeddedMontiArc Model](#)
- MathUnit model with MatrixModifier subcomponents
 - graphical C&C Model; layout is automatically generated
[Open Graphical Model](#)
 - [Published Textual EmbeddedMontiArc Model](#)

4 TOOLCHAIN

EmbeddedMontiArc Production and Test Compiler.

Examples of HTML files (produced by our EmbeddedMontiArc compiler) to test C&C Models with concrete values directly in the web-browser are available under:

Middleware Plugins.

Here, we embed the videos which we mentioned in our paper to show the different middlewares coupled with our EmbeddedMontiArc compiler.

Here, we embed the videos mentioned in the paper showing our EmbeddedMontiArc development environment.

Try out our simple online car simulator being a light-weighted version of the third video:

- [Online Car Simulator](#)
- [generated graphical C&C layout of car controller](#)
- [textual EmbeddedMontiArc car controller models](#)

6 CASE STUDY

Models/Code

- [EmbeddedMontiArc](#)
- Simulink
 - [Simulink Web-Export of ObjectDetector](#)
 - [Simulink Web-Export of MathUnit](#)
 - [Download all Simulink slx-files \(R2018a version\) as ZIP file](#)
 - [Simulink Error for MathUnit model \(matrix dimensions are too large\)](#)
- MATLAB
 - [Published m-files for ObjectDetector](#)
 - [Published m-file for MathUnit](#)
 - [Download all MATLAB m-files \(R2018a version\) as ZIP file](#)
- JavaScript: [MathJS/NumericJS](#)
 - [Published JavaScript code for ObjectDetector \(without k-means\)](#)
 - [Published JavaScript code for MathUnit](#)
- Java: [RelativeGPS](#)
 - [Published Java code for ObjectDetector \(without k-means\)](#)
 - [Published Java code for MathUnit](#)
 - [Download all Java IntelliJ projects as ZIP file](#)
- OpenModelica
 - >
 - [Download all OpenModelica models as ZIP file \(ca. 400 MB\)](#)

EmbeddedMontiArc Compiler

- [C++ Code Generator @ Github](#)
- [WebAssembly Toolchain inclusive HTML Adapter Generator @ Github](#)
- [Download \(ca. 260 MB\) EmbeddedMontiArc Compiler Toolchain as Windows 64-bit portable app \(including Armadillo-Backend tests for all four applications presented in this paper\)](#)
- [Download \(ca. 1.1 GB\) EmbeddedMontiArcStudio 1.5.2 as Windows 64-bit portable app \(Development Environment for EmbeddedMontiArc\) - uses older version of EmbeddedMontiArc compiler](#)

Runtime Performance Results

For some measurements we added the videos for the runtime performance analysis to [this youtube playlist](#).

Comparison of Runtime Performance of Code Compiled by EmbeddedMontiArc
With other Existing Compiler/Interpreter Frameworks
(Windows 10 64-bit; Intel Core i7-6700HQ)

Credits

I, Michael von Wenckstern, want to thank all the students who supported us developing EmbeddedMontiArc; specially I want to thank **Jean-Marc Ronck**, who set up the entire IDE and helped us by the WebAssembly toolchain; and **Stefan Brunecker**, who integrated the emscripten toolchain into our EMA compiler toolchain.